

Integrated Marketing Communication to Influencing International Standard Energy Economy Car Buying Decision of Consumers in Bangkok

Pisit Potjanajaruwit

Abstract—The objective of this research was to study the influence of Integrated Marketing Communication on Buying Decision of Consumers in Bangkok. A total of 397 respondents were collected from customers who drive in Bangkok. A questionnaire was utilized as a tool to collect data. Statistics utilized in this research included frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and multiple regression analysis. Data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences.

The findings revealed that the majority of respondents were male with the age between 25-34 years old, hold undergraduate degree, married and stay together. The average income of respondents was between 10,001-20,000 baht. In terms of occupation, the majority worked for private companies. The effect to the Buying Decision of Consumers in Bangkok to including sale promotion with the low interest and discount for an installment, selling by introducing and gave product information through sales persons, public relation by website, direct marketing by annual motor show and advertisement by television media.

Keywords—ECO Car, Integrated Marketing Communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

AS the Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) become a result of social media impact, but they also say that social media present only a part of IMC strategy and of an integrated marketing strategy. Researcher states that social media requires integration with traditional marketing [1]

Social media's marketing potential is lost if it is not woven into the overall marketing strategy. The tools and strategies for communicating with customers have changed significantly with the emergence of the social media. The researcher suggests the creation of ecosystem of related elements involving both digital and traditional media, strategic integration of social media into a firm's marketing communications strategy, and social media marketing as a mandatory element of their marketing strategy. They conclude that it is no longer enough to merely incorporate social media as standalone elements of a marketing plan. Companies need to consider both social and traditional media as part of an ecosystem whereby all elements work together toward a common objective. Marketing managers are seeking ways to incorporate social media into their IMC strategies. Researcher propose that social media be considered a hybrid component of the promotional mix and therefore be incorporated as an

integral part of the organization's IMC strategy. They compare and contrast the traditional communications paradigm that relied on the established promotional mix, elements which were developed and refined over the past 100 years, with the new communications paradigm which incorporates social media. [2]

First, in a traditional sense social media enable companies to talk to their customers, and this role of social media is consistent with the use of traditional IMC tools. Second, in a non-traditional sense social media enable customers to talk directly to one another - it is an extension of traditional word-of-mouth communication. Third, social media also enable customers to talk to companies, which is important for marketing research. [1]

The content, timing, and frequency of the social media based conversations occurring between consumers are outside managers' direct control. This stands in contrast to the traditional integrated marketing communications paradigm whereby a high degree of control is present." So, according to the new communications paradigm, presented by Mangold and Faulds communications are performed integrally - by combining traditional promotion mix (advertising, personal selling, public relations and publicity, direct marketing and sales promotion) and social media (blogs - company sponsored and user sponsored, social networking sites, video sharing sites. [1]

With the development of digital media, consumers change their behavior, so that they redirect from traditional (classic) to digital media. However, consumers use different media, i.e. the mix of media, so that organizations also need to create messages for different media, i.e. a different acceptance of media by the consumers. Fig. 1 shows an integrated approach to the media - both traditional and new digital. [2]

Consumers use traditional media such as newspapers (print), magazines, radio, television, direct media - telephone, mail, catalogues, external advertising etc. In addition to these typical traditional media, other instruments of marketing mix are equally important. These instruments are not directly focused on the promotion but they can be considered media as well and they represent product organization. Nowadays when consumers are constantly "bombarded" by advertising messages and when they do not pay attention to them, it is necessary to have media which would attract the attention of consumers. Such media can be effective packaging. [1]

To be specific, consumers can avoid watching TV video clips, they can choose not to listen to radio messages, look at

all billboards and thus to avoid influences of typical media. However, when they find themselves in a store, an effective packaging can attract and keep the attention more than any other media. Price also "tells" a lot about the product, so it is an indirect medium. Distribution channels, retailers (knowledge, kindness, politeness, etc.), the process of service delivery, cordial atmosphere additionally represent product/organization. As a result of the aforementioned influences of media, traditional - offline consumers, through oral recommendation ("word of mouth" - in person), communicate their (dis)pleasure to others, and thus they become the most important i.e. the most influential "movable media.[2]

The process of digitalisation influences the acceptance of new digital media like the Internet, mobile phones and other mobile devices (e.g. iPad), digital newspapers and magazines (through the Internet and mobile phones), digital radio, digital TV and digital consumers. Online consumers can quickly convey messages to multiple people - friends, acquaintances, but also to strangers.

The Internet, digital radio, digital TV, mobile phones and other mobile devices are used as:

- Media - channels of communication (as a part of multi-channel - integrated marketing communications) - for communications, interactions and relationships with customers and other actors in the micro-environment, [3]
- Sales channels,
- Distribution channels - for digital products,
- The method of marketing research - consumers and all other actors and forces in the region.

As the researcher states, every element in marketing mix of an organization - whether traditional or online - should share a consistent look and feel that aligns with company's goals. Consumers behave differently; they use different media, so organisations use

IMC. Digital communications are only a part of multi-channel, i.e. integrated communications. The real question is what mix of marketing communications should be used. Based on integrated marketing communications, organisation informs, persuades, reminds us "listens" to consumers about products/services and/or organisation.[2]

The methods of integrated marketing communications are:

- Advertising - paid form of non-personal presentation of products or services of an organisation.
- Sales promotion - includes a variety of short-term incentives that encourage trial and / or purchase of products or services.
- Public relations and publicity are aimed to create and maintain a good image of an organization.

Traditional ways of direct communication like using mail, telephone, fax in order to establish direct communications and interactions.

- Personal selling is an interaction face-to-face between dealer and one or more potential buyers in order to organise presentations, answer questions, and obtain orders and product sales.
- Digital marketing communications - using the Internet, databases, mobile devices, digital radio and TV, and other

(for the time being) new digital technologies for faster and more effective communications, interactions and the management of relationship with customers and other actors in the internal environment.[3]

The above mentioned classic forms of communication, thanks to digital technology, get their appropriate digital forms. For example, the advertising in classic (traditional) printed newspapers and magazines on one hand, and advertising in digital newspapers and magazines (online and mobile) are different. Classic TV is replaced by Internet TV and digital TV. Telephone communications are being diverted from landline phones to mobile phones. Mobile phones allow communications with mobile consumers - i.e. consumers on the move - anytime, anywhere - of course, if the consumers are interested in communications. Smart phones offer numerous possibilities for both consumers and organisations. [2]

In addition to traditional and digital methods of marketing communications, organizations present their products / services through non-communicative instruments of the marketing mix. All this together makes integrated marketing communications.

Non-communicative instruments of marketing mix - product (above all brand and packaging), price, channels of distribution, people, process, physical evidence. All these instruments also "speak" a lot about the product and the organization. In other words, all instruments of marketing mix directly or indirectly represent products/services/organizations and can contribute to the value of products and to the experience of consumers.[2]The communications among of consumers are related to recommendations ,comments, suggestions, reviews etc.

All previously mentioned forms of IMC have great influence on WOM. This, and not the significance of WOM, is the reason why WOM is listed last. If we talk about their significance, WOM should be listed first. Numerous research results confirm that communications with family members, friends, acquaintances and customers have greater impact on consumers' behavior than IMC of organisations. [3]

Communications among users can be offline (e.g. from mouth to mouth) and online (e.g. through forums, blogs, social networks and other social media). The following terms are used: User Generated Media and User Generated Content.

Availability, prices and acceptance of new digital media by greater number of consumers - market, will in the end lead to the consumers via digital media take control over the consumption , they can be active participants and passive observers and not only the recipients of information. Nowadays, communications can be initiated by both organizations and consumers.[3]

Integrated Marketing Communication such as Traditional organization's monologue to consumers and stakeholders through traditional media is being supplemented by digital media that allow two-way communications and dialogue between consumers and organization, but also among consumers themselves.

Before the advent of digital media, in order to promote themselves organisations used traditional media such as newspapers (print), magazines, radio, television, direct media - telephone, mail, catalogues, external advertising methods, other "specific media": product (especially the brand, packaging, price, distribution channels, people; process; physical evidence.

When digital media have been invented, consumers started increasingly to use them, so the companies had to start to communicate through digital media like the Internet, mobile phones and other mobile devices (e.g. iPad etc.), digital newspapers and magazines (via the Internet and mobile devices), digital radio, digital TV, digital consumers - digital WOM. Consumers use both traditional and digital media, so that integration in terms of media means that organisations also use all media in the process of IMC.

Before the advent of digital media, organisations were conducting promotion based on traditional promotion mix - advertising, personal selling, public relations & publicity, direct marketing, sales promotion. With the advent of digital media, organisations have begun to use also digital communication / interaction. [3]

Integration, in terms of methods of communications, means that organisations use both traditional promotion and digital communications, but they have to pay attention to WOM communications as well, and to stimulate them through word-of-Mouth Marketing - WOMM

Before the advent of digital media, organisations were able to promote brands through traditional static forms (of promotion) based on "monologue towards mass target audience. Digital media have provided opportunity for more dynamic communications - interactions in real time - real dialogues with" all interested users (of digital media).

Research will propose that the next stage of evolution of mass customization is customization - a buyer-centric company strategy that combines mass customization with customized marketing. Digital technologies and consumers will affect more and more the customerization of marketing and business activities u as a whole. In the old model-mass and segmented marketing, [3]

Communications were reduced to advertising and PR. In the new model, marketing communications are integrated, interactive, and customized. Consumers education and entertainment, or as some authors call it "interactive edutainment", are also very important. The customerization of the content, format, the educational component and the entertainment/ captivating power of the communication, its mode of delivery, and timing and place are becoming important to a segment of customers and will become an increasingly important part of the portfolio of communication activities of the firm.[3]

Before the advent of digital media, the key initiators and actors in communications, especially in the promotion, were organizations. Digital media have provided opportunity for consumers to be active participants and initiators of communications. Integration in terms of actors means that

both consumers and organizations take part in communications. [2]

Since Toffler has first invented the term the presumed, numerous authors, talk about the importance of prosumers and prosumption, presume age, age of the digital prosumer and presumed capitalism who is both producer and consumer; and presumption involves a combination of production and consumption. Presumption has always existed, but various social changes (e.g., the rise of the Internet and of social networking on it) have greatly expanded both the practice of presumption and scholarly attention to it

Before the advent of digital media, content was usually created by organisations (excluding offline WOM communication). However, with the advent of digital media content can be created by consumers as well, who are the users of digital media. Integration in terms of content creation means that the organisation apart from content marketing has to pay attention to user-generated content. User-generated content represents "another way of saying presumption.[3]

II. METHODOLOGY

The objectives of this research:

1. To study personal characteristics of purchasing decision among consumers in Bangkok.
2. To study influence of integrated marketing communication with purchasing decision on ECO car of the consumers.

Research Hypotheses

Based on literature survey the following hypotheses have been derived:

1. Different personal characteristics affect the decision to buy energy-efficient cars of different standards.
2. The integrated marketing communication relate to the decision to purchase a car with universal power of consumers in Bangkok.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

In this study will provide a conceptual framework for promotions mixed will using Phillip Kotler and refer to purchasing decision model by S-R Theory (A Model of Consumer Behavior) range of promotion techniques designed within a promotion mixed framework that effect to consumer purchasing decision follow by this framework [1].

III. FINDING

The findings disclosed that the majority were male between 25-34 years old, married and live together. The majority had an undergraduate degree working for private companies. The average income of the respondents was between 10,001 - 20,000 baht. The respondents rated the Integrated Marketing Communication mixed of product, price, place, promotion, people, physical environment, and process as high. For every three months, the average driving was 5 times. The average purchase was about 150,396 baht. Most of the time, consumers would purchase eco-car. The main reasons for choosing Eco-car included convenient location for travel and often come to purchase by themselves. The best time to come was between 13.01-15.00 PM.

The hypothesis testing results revealed that consumers with a different age had the difference in their purchasing behavior in terms of the frequency of purchasing with the 0.05 level of significance. Moreover, the marketing mix: price, place, and product had the correlation coefficient of 0.921, 0.949, and 0.591 respectively. These three variables could predict the frequency that consumers prefer to shop for every three months [4]. Whereas, the marketing mix: physical environment, process had the correlation coefficient of 2980.97 and 2188.09 respectively. These two variables could predict the how much customers will spend each trip or the expenses which was purchasing of consumer decision found is a product dimension consumer buying decision that the basic economy car energy because of oil consumption is not more than 5 liters/100 kilometers.

IV. DISCUSSIONS/SUGGESTIONS

The findings revealed that consumers with difference in age had different purchasing behavior during a period of three months with the 0.05 level of significance. The customers who had the age of 24 years old or below purchased less frequently than the customers who had the age of 25-34 years old. The average difference between two groups was about 2.07 trips. This result concurred with the research of who studied the factors of decision making in the moving weekend market, a case study of [5] which showed that customers with age difference had a difference purchasing behavior The reason of this difference may come from the fact that customers with the age of 25-34 years old were employed customers with income and tended to be interested in buying new house and house decoration.

The integrated Marketing Communication in terms of Advertising, Public Relation, Personal Selling, Sale Promotion and Direct Marketing were the factors that affected the purchasing behavior in terms of the frequency in purchasing during a period of three months. Therefore, the business owners should focus more on those factors and it should encourage more purchases. This result concurred with the study of the factors of the marketing mix for consumers who purchased souvenirs at Damien community, Dusit district, Bangkok and his results showed that marketing mix in terms of product, price, and promotion had a huge influence on

consumer purchasing [4]. His study also found that the integrated Marketing Communication in terms of physical environment and process had an influence in terms of the amount of purchasing in each trip. The result also agreed with the study of who drive a car about the factors related to purchasing behavior of the consumers at Bangkok and reported that the Integrated Marketing Communication overall had the influence on consumer purchasing behavior.

V. RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The finding revealed that the customers with the age between 24-35 years old came to shop more frequent and with larger amount of expenses than any other group and they often chose to buy house decoration items. The reasons for shop at the Bangkok car market included convenient of location and means of transportation. These customers often shop between 13.01-15.00 PM [5]. Therefore, it would be advantages to use this information to set up a strategic marketing plan to get more market share. The findings revealed also that the Integrated Marketing Communication in terms of physical environment and process is important and had a coefficient value of 2980.97 which was the highest value. Therefore, the management of the Bangkok car shop should consider enhancing the physical environment to attract more customers; things such as the cleanliness of the market, the proper light, the space for parking. The second highest value of coefficient was the process, with the value of 21.88.09. Therefore, the management should consider things such as focus more on the proper time opening and closing, the correctness of checking the merchandise, the fast and correctness at the cashiers, the insurance or warranty of the products, and the quality of product delivery.

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